

FIRM

FEHRL INFRASTRUCTURE RESEARCH MAGAZINE

FLOW PROJECT NOW ENDED AFTER FINAL CONFERENCE, SEVERAL EVENTS AND KEY PUBLICATIONS p.10-11

FEHRL organised key FLOW events in France and Lithuania

AM4INFRA PROJECT HOLDS FINAL CONFERENCE AT TRA2018 p.12-13

Event included outcomes of three Living Labs in Rome, Eindhoven and London

FEHRL AT TRA2018 AND TEN-T DAYS 2018 WITH SEVERAL KEY H2020 AND FP7 PROJECTS

Projects featured in rollup and videos on stands, in key sessions and presentations (p. 6-8)

PUBLISHED BY**FEHRL**

Boulevard de la Woluwe 42/b3
1200 Brussels
Belgium
Tel. +32 2 775 82 45
www.fehrl.org
ISSN: 2294-8295

**INNOVATION FOR TRANSPORT
INFRASTRUCTURE**

Transport infrastructure is the lifeblood of modern society, but often struggles to meet demands and expectations on reliability, availability, maintainability, safety, environment, health and cost. FEHRL's role is to provide solutions for the challenges now faced and anticipate the challenges to come. Through innovation, the operation of transport infrastructure can address society's needs.

FEHRL encourages collaborative research into topics such as mobility, transport and infrastructure, energy, environment and resources, safety and security as well as design and production.

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Most of the projects covered are supported by funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme.

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WELCOME

to the twelfth issue of FEHRL's Infrastructure Research Magazine (FIRM), which outlines how FEHRL provides transport infrastructure solutions for current and future challenges. This issue features the highlights of FEHRL's contribution to the 2018 edition of the Transport Research Arena (TRA2018), as well as the TEN-T Days 2018 event, which were both held in April 2018. At TRA2018, FEHRL and some of its members were present again on the CEDR stand, and FEHRL also organised the final conference for the H2020 AM4INFRA project as a side event and the FORx4 network launch as a reception. Many of our projects also featured on the European Commission (EC) stand and in various technical sessions of the conference. See pages 6-8 for the key details of these.

FEHRL also supported the TRA VISIONS 2018 competition at TRA2018 with the communication (see page 19) and is becoming more deeply involved in the organisation of TRA with the launch of the new TRA2020 CSA project (see page 9) and its contribution to Work Package 5 (WP5) of the H2020 SETRIS project, which has just ended at the end of April 2018 (see related article on this page).

Also in this issue, you can read updates on the H2020 FLOW final conference (p.10-11), RAGTIME (p.14), SAFE 10-T (p.15), AEROBI (p.16), SENSKIN (p.17) and SKILLFUL (p.18) projects and a first announcement on the back page for the ERA-NET Plus Infravation final conference in Rotterdam, the Netherlands, on 4th October 2018.

We hope you enjoy your read!

Thierry Goger
FEHRL Secretary General
(thierry.goger@fehrl.org)

SETRIS PAVES THE WAY TO TRA2020

In the frame of WP5, SETRIS supported and shaped the development of the future TRA by providing inputs on all aspects (strategic, financial, practical and organisational) of the event in view to make it the leading European conference for dialogue on transport research between industry, academia and public authorities for future mobility solutions.

The SETRIS project has provided key contributions for assuring a smooth transition from one conference to a new one, to support the continuous development of the conference, and to consolidate it, by both gathering the experience gained from the previous years and issuing further recommendations to guarantee the sustainability of the future conferences. In fact, besides supporting the participation of the different European Technology Platforms (ETPs) to the different TRA Committees of the 2016 and 2018 conferences, SETRIS has developed a number of practical guidelines and recommendations on the overall TRA aspects. The project has operated according to the TRA Management Committee's orientations and produced the different deliverables on that basis. This material is aimed to be practical and serve for the transfer of knowledge between hosts in view of assuring swift continuity in the Conference organisation. Such deliverables were due to be fully presented to the new host before the summer.

The SETRIS final report can be found at trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/strengthening-european-transport-research-and-innovation-strategies#tab-docs. The final SETRIS event took the form of a "Strategic Session" at TRA2018 entitled "Towards a Truly Integrated Transport System" on 16th April 2018.

► For more information on FEHRL, see:

- www.linkedin.com/company/fehrl
- twitter.com/FEHRL_comms
- www.facebook.com/FEHRLSecretariat

MESSAGE FROM FEHRL'S PRESIDENT

CLOSER TO IMPLEMENTATION?

Implementation is the art of putting a decision, research result or plan into effect. Implementation is the achievement of earned value in a process or research programme. In the last years, both in EU calls and other research programmes, the expectations towards innovation from research have increased. This is very positive in the sense that the resulting innovation will show the benefits of research, but still provides a much-needed dilemma for pure research.

FEHRL members are mainly research providers. FEHRL members pay more and more attention to bridging the gap between research and implementation on the basis of their own research results. We aim to disseminate research results in a way that is as concrete as possible to fulfil implementation needs. FEHRL as an organisation has the objectives to “provide scientific input to policy on road and infrastructure matters; create and maintain an efficient and safe road and infrastructure network; increase innovation in road and infrastructure construction and related industries; improve the energy efficiency of road and infrastructure engineering and operations; and protect the environment and improve the quality of life.” To fulfil these objectives, FEHRL has to be active in the field of implementation. One good example is the ERA-NET Plus Infravation where FEHRL has been a key player representing academia in a partnership with government bodies and industry – the so called ‘triple helix concept’.

Some sectors of industry have a long tradition of being committed to research. For the transport sector, the tradition of research seems to be a bit scarcer. FEHRL members represent academia and have to seek partners in industry and cooperate with governments to produce implementable research. Over the past years, FEHRL has developed a strong collaboration with the industry. This gives a positive impact to facilitating the connection between FEHRL institutes and local industry players, which will enhance the innovation and implementation aspects. This collaboration will also most likely be useful in facilitating the link between Industry and FEHRL customers.

There are many good examples of research programmes where FEHRL is involved. All of them show that cooperation between rather different actors pays off. My wish for the ongoing and future programmes is that cooperation and shared knowledge across participants, combined with individual excellence, appear as highly valued qualities. If so, our research will give even better results and added value for the entire transport sector.

Marit Brandtsegg
FEHRL President
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FEHRL AT TRA2018 AND TEN-T DAYS 2018 WITH SEVERAL KEY H2020 AND FP7 PROJECTS

HIGHLIGHTS OF TRA2018 INCLUDED AM4INFRA FINAL CONFERENCE AND LAUNCH OF FORX4 RECEPTION

The FEHRL Secretariat initiated or was involved in countless project-related activities at the **Transport Research Arena 2018 (TRA2018)** in Vienna, Austria on 16-19th April 2018. As well as supporting co-organiser AustriaTech with the overall communications for the event, FEHRL was present with members BRRC, IFSTTAR and VTI for the whole of TRA2018 on the FEHRL part of the CEDR stand that FEHRL also helped to produce. Several projects featured as part of the official TRA2018 programme and both the CEDR and European Commission (EC) stands included a dynamic programme of activities on their exhibition areas, including the ones mentioned in this article. FEHRL also supported the **TRA VISIONS 2018** competition (see page 19) with communications and helped out at the ERTRAC stand through the **FUTURE-RADAR** project.

Highlights of the week included the launch of the **FORx4** network in the CEDR Agora exhibition area on Tuesday 17th April and the **AM4INFRA** final conference on Wednesday 18th April, as featured on page 7. See www.fehrl.org/knowledge-transfer/events/tra2018 for a detailed overview of all FEHRL's activities at TRA2018.

PROJECTS IN THE TRA2018 PROGRAMME, ON THE CEDR AND EC STANDS

The following ongoing and completed projects featured as part of the overall TRA2018 technical programme, as well as on the Agora area of the CEDR stand and EC stand of the exhibition.

The **CoEXist** project featured both as a Marketplace Poster and as a project poster in the Technical session "Automated Transport: Modelling, Evaluation, Validation & Testing" on Tuesday 17th April, as well as on the FEHRL part of the CEDR stand.

Meanwhile, Randy Rzewnicki, ECF Policy Officer, presented the **FLOW** project in the Agora area on Wednesday 18th April 2018 and the project featured on the FEHRL part of the CEDR stand. Read more about FLOW on pages 10-11.

The **ERA-NET Plus Infravation** programme and projects featured on the FEHRL part of the CEDR stand and in the Agora area with the following presentations:

- Giovanni Dotelli, Politecnico di Milano, presented the **SEACON** project on Monday 16th April
- Richard van der Elburg, Rijkswaterstaat and David García Sánchez, Tecnalia, presented the **Infravation** programme and **FASSTbridge** project on Wednesday 18th April.

Read more about the Infravation Final Event in Rotterdam, the Netherlands, on 4th October 2018 on the advert on the back page.

The **FASSTBRIDGE** project also featured along with a **RAGTIME** project poster in the Technical session "Asset Management and Life Cycle Analysis" on Wednesday 18th April. The new RAGTIME video also featured both on the FEHRL part of the CEDR stand and the EC stand. Read more about RAGTIME on page 14.

Julie Clarke, **SAFE-10-T** Project Manager, presented the project's objectives and approach, as well as the current outcome and expected impact of each Work Packages on the EC stand on Thursday 19th April and the new video was featured on the FEHRL part of the CEDR stand. Read more about SAFE-10-T on page 15.

The **SENSKIN** project also featured on the FEHRL part of the CEDR stand with a new video and was presented by Project Coordinator Angelos Amitidis of ICCS on the EC stand on Monday 16th April and by Claudia Ciuca of FEHRL in the Technical session "Transport Infrastructure: Application of Machine Learning" on Tuesday 17th April. Read more about SENSKIN on page 17.

Three completed projects that FEHRL was involved in were also featured in Technical Sessions at TRA2018. Claudia Ciuca presented the **ECORoads** project results in the "Road Infrastructure Analysis, Management & Improvements" session on Wednesday 18th April.

On the same day, Martin Lamb of Maple Consulting presented the **USE-IT and FOX** projects in the "Travel and Transportation Planning" session and on Thursday 19th April, several members of the

REFINET Consortium made the project presentation in the "Infrastructure as a Part of Mobility/Society System" session.

These activities were of course in addition to countless other parts of the programme that involved FEHRL members and key partners.

LAUNCH OF FORx4 AND RECEPTION AT TRA2018

Thanks to the support of the EC, the community of transport infrastructure has built a vision for an integrated infrastructure for seamless mobility, with its necessary need for Research, Demonstration and Implementation (R&D&I). The main coordinators of the initiative, FEHRL (Thierry Goger, FEHRL Secretary General) and European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP) (Alain Zarli, ECTP Secretary General), pitched the main outline of the FORx4 programme and discussed the way forward on **Tuesday 17th April 2018** on the CEDR stand at TRA2018! FORx4 inspired the USE-iT and FOX projects and will be the vehicle by which the results of these and the REFINET project and expert networks continues in the future. A special thank you was given to Cristina Marolda of DG Mobility and Transport (DG MOVE) of the EC who was about to retire and has given extensive support to FEHRL and FORx4, as well as the USE-iT and FOX and REFINET projects.

For more details on FORx4, join the FORx4 initiative on transport infrastructure LinkedIn group or contact Thierry Goger at thierry.goger@fehrl.org or Martin Lamb at martin.lamb@maple-consulting.uk.

AM4INFRA FINAL CONFERENCE AS SIDE EVENT OF TRA 2018

The AM4INFRA consortium held its Final Event on Wednesday 18th April 2018 at TRA2018. The Final Conference was held in two consecutive sessions with identical agendas, in order to enable delegates to choose the one most convenient in relation to the rest of their TRA2018 schedule.

Participants had the opportunity to get an overview of the AM4INFRA project, and its (draft) results that constitute a common framework approach for asset management on transport infrastructures that is cross asset, cross modal and cross border. Those who were unable to attend could follow via web streaming or join the webinar on Thursday 3rd May 2018. For more details, see the related article on pages 12-13.

AM4INFRA was also presented by Ramesh Sinhal of Highways England on the EC stand on Thursday 19th April and featured on the CEDR stand.

FEHRL TOOK PART IN TEN-T DAYS ON 25-27TH APRIL 2018

The H2020 and FP7 projects **AEROBI**, **CoExist**, **ERA-NET Plus Infravation**, **FLOW**, **RAGTIME**, **SAFE 10 T**, **SENSKIN**, **SKILLFUL** that FEHRL is involved in all featured on one stand and TRA2020 and TRA VISIONS 2018 on a second stand opposite the first one in the exhibition of the **TEN-T Days 2018** organised in Ljubljana, Slovenia by DG MOVE for some 2000 participants on 25-27th April 2018. These stands, located in a prime position next to the plenary room entrance and between two automotive suppliers, were visited by a variety of key scientific and policy stakeholders from all modes of transport and various countries during the three-day high-level event.

Key visitors to the stand included European Commissioner for Transport, Violeta Bulc, who heard about the innovative solutions from FEHRL Secretary General Thierry Goger for H2020-funded transport infrastructure along with Alan Haigh, Head of the H2020 Department at INEA dealing with Energy and Transport, as well as Finnish Minister of Transport and Communications, Anne Berner, to discuss the next Transport Research Arena; TRA2020, to be held in Helsinki, Finland in April 2020 (see page 9).

During the event, Thierry Goger also advocated transport as independent pillar in FP9 to Member of the European Parliament's Committee on Transport and Tourism, Gesine Meissner.

In addition, the H2020 FLOW and AEROBI projects were presented as three-minute pitches by Thierry Goger at the event's Future of Mobility Ideas Accelerator and Futuristic Lab in the Digital and Safety sessions, respectively on Wednesday 25th April, and the H2020 CoExist project by Siegfried Rupprecht of Rupprecht Consult at the Cities session of the same Ideas Accelerator and Futuristic Lab on the same day.

See www.fehrl.org/knowledge-transfer/events/10tdays for a detailed overview of all FEHRL's activities at TEN-T Days 2018 and tentdays.eu/2018 for an overview of the TEN-T Days 2018.

Handover from Austrian to Finnish team at first MC meeting on 7th June

Finnish Minister of Transport and Communications Anne Berner and FEHRL Secretary General Thierry Goger supporting TRA2020 at TEN-T Days 2018.

TRA2018 HANDS OVER THE BATON TO TRA2020

The next edition of the Transport Research Arena (TRA) conference, TRA 2020, will take place at the Messukeskus Expo and Convention Centre in the capital of Finland, Helsinki, from 26-30th April 2020. With the theme of “Enabling the transformation – transport and mobility (r)evolution for smart, green and integrated society” TRA 2020 will showcase the disruption of transport and mobility RDI, as well as ways to enable and foster a Europe-wide transformation in all transport modes.

To mark the succession of one successful Austrian TRA 2018 to another successful Finnish TRA 2020, Ingolf Schädler from the Austrian Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology and Chair of the TRA Management Committee (MC), handed over the baton in the form of a special TRA plaque to Anne Berner, Finnish Minister for Transport, on Thursday 19th April 2018 at the TRA 2018 Closing Session. Minister Berner then gave a short speech to welcome all the participants to Helsinki for TRA 2020.

As well as this, TRA 2020 was already quite visible at TRA 2018 with a booth in a prominent location of the exhibition. The stand featured a dynamic programme of pitch sessions by key Finnish projects, initiatives and companies on 17th-18th April and key speeches on 19th April to welcome participants to TRA 2020 by Anne Berner, as well as Signe Ratso, Deputy Director General, DG Research and Innovation of the European Commission and Steve Phillips, Secretary General of CEDR.

Led by the Finnish Transport Safety Agency Trafi, the Finnish Consortium supporting the organisation of TRA 2020 includes the Finnish Ministry of Transport and Communications, the Finnish Transport Agency, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, City of Helsinki, Aalto University, Metropolia, Tampere Univer-

sity of Technology, Helsinki Region Transport HSL, Finnish Marine Industries, ITS Finland, Business Finland, Forum Virium Helsinki, Helsinki Business HUB, Smart & Clean, Growth Corridor Finland, the Finnish Communications Regulatory Authority (FICORA), the Finnish Meteorological Institute.

As the practical organiser of the conference, VTT is also the Coordinator of the Horizon 2020 CSA TRA 2020 project, which held its kick off meeting in Brussels, Belgium on 2nd May and first Consortium meeting in Helsinki on 6th June. The CSA TRA 2020 project will assist and contribute to the organisation of the event, especially the TRA Committees and the host country/national organisation. The CSA TRA 2020 project features Aalto University, TRA2018 co-organiser AustriaTech, City of Helsinki, ECTRI, FEHRL and the Finnish Transport Agency. FEHRL leads the Work Package (WP) 3 on communication in the project, and is also involved in WP5, which will provide recommendations for the future editions of TRA.

Since TRA 2018, TRA 2020 has already featured at the TEN-T Days 2018 in Ljubljana, Slovenia on 25-27th April (see page 8) and the International Transport Forum (ITF) Summit in Leipzig, Germany from 23-25th May. The first MC meeting was held in Helsinki on 7th June.

MAIN ORGANISERS

CO-ORGANISER

OTHER CSA PARTNERS

► For more information, contact Alina Koskela, Chair of the TRA 2020 National Secretariat at alina.koskela@trafi.fi and Eveliina Grönroos, Project Manager of the TRA2020 Conference Project at eveliina.gronroos@vtt.fi. The website at www.traconference.eu and social media will be updated with new information about TRA2020.

[Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#) [YouTube](#) [Facebook](#) [Instagram](#) #TRA2020 and #TRA2020project

Images from FLOW and TRACE final conference.

FLOW PROJECT NOW ENDED AFTER FINAL CONFERENCE, SEVERAL EVENTS AND KEY PUBLICATIONS

The EU-funded CIVITAS FLOW (Furthering Less Congestion by Creating Opportunities For More Walking and Cycling) and TRACE (Walking and Cycling Tracking Services) projects have brought data from tracking trips and transport modelling up to a 21st century level. Since the new year and after three years of research, the H2020 FLOW project has been wrapping up its activities, which included the final conference and several events organised by FEHRL. On 13-14th March 2018 in Brussels, FLOW and TRACE joined forces and held their joint final conference for more than 200 registered urban transport professionals, entitled: "Decongesting Europe: New approaches to freeing our cities". Both projects have worked with transport data and developed new ways to boost walking and cycling as a way to reduce congestion.

Congestion reduction award for Goudappel Coffeng:

The consultancy Goudappel Coffeng was awarded the FLOW Congestion Reduction Award. Goudappel Coffeng developed a new multi-modal traffic model that even differentiates between regular bicycles and e-bikes, uses the FLOW tools in a very creative way and thereby contributes to put walking and cycling on equal footing in the transport planning process of their client cities.

The interactive event discussed how walking and cycling can help reduce congestion on urban roads and included training sessions, presentations, breakout sessions, a TRACE "tracking tour", political debates and a world café. It also featured an award as well as a declaration signed by high level decision makers.

#MAKEALLMODESCOUNT:

Ciarán Cuffe, Councillor of Dublin was first to sign the #MakeAllModes-Count declaration at the conference, stating: "We believe in making all modes count in urban transport. Let's put walking and cycling on an equal footing with other modes to reduce the impacts of congestion!"

Professionals across Europe interested in results at several events organised by FEHRL

In the last months of the project, FEHRL has organised workshops in France and Lithuania to present the results to key decision-makers. On 23rd April 2018, FEHRL Secretary General Thierry Goger presented the main challenges of the mobility of the 21st century as well as some tangible solutions for soft transport modes (cycling and walking) to 30 French local policy-makers in the region of Saint Malo, France. The city mayors were very happy to learn about the short to medium-term innovation in the field of transport and transport infrastructure. They were also positively surprised about the qualitative

"We have to make the best use of our road space. Pedestrians and cyclists use space more efficiently than private cars. The future of cities is about walkability, bikeability and liveability", said Dublin's Councillor Ciarán Cuffe.

Other panelists included political decision makers from Belgrade, SRM Bologna, Jerusalem, Transport for Greater Manchester and Valencia.

Images from FLOW at TRA2018 and TEN-T Days 2018.

and quantitative evidence of the benefit of walking and cycling to mobility not only in cities but also in peri-urban and rural areas.

Another FLOW workshop was organised on 30th April 2018 at Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VGTU) in Vilnius, Lithuania for around 40 stakeholders to discuss how walking and cycling can help reduce congestion on urban roads. The welcome speech was given by Audrius Vaitkus, director of the Road Research Institute (RRI VGTU). Thierry Goger then presented the future challenges and needs for research and development of transport infrastructure. Participants had a great opportunity to get an overview of the FLOW project results that constitute how walking and cycling can help to reduce congestion. Adewole Adesiyun, FEHRL Deputy Secretary General, shared the FLOW project's experience and results from six partner cities which have been working with the FLOW created tools over the past three years, applying them to a number of cycling and walking measures.

FEHRL Secretary General also advocated the great benefit of walking and cycling in urban mobility but also in peri-urban and rural environments for FLOW to a large audience including Commissioner Bulc at the Ideas Accelerator and Futuristic Lab of the TEN-T Days 2018 on Wednesday 26th April 2018 (see page 8). And Randy Rzewnicki, ECF Policy Officer, presented FLOW on the CEDR stand D02 at the 2018 Transport Research Arena (TRA2018) on Wednesday 18th April 2018 (see page 7).

OVERVIEW OF LATEST FLOW PUBLICATIONS AND TOOLS

1. Roadmap encouraging private sector to use multimodal transport analysis techniques

FLOW released a new publication: Using FLOW's Multimodal Transport Analysis Techniques in the Transport Planning Profession. This document outlines how transport sector businesses can use the FLOW approach to help clients and administrations better ask, and answer, questions about the impacts of walking and cycling measures.

These include transport planning and engineering consultants as well as producers of transport equipment and supplies (e.g., pavement systems or cycling rack builders). It can assist such businesses in communicating improved methods for analysing multimodal transport system performance.

2. FLOW tools available on project website

An actual user guide (for cities i.e.) has also been produced in seven languages that includes new recommendations. The backbone of the project, the FLOW tools have all been finalised and are accessible via the FLOW website. This includes FLOW's Impact Assessment Tool and guidelines how to use it. You can now use the Excel tool with the accompanying guidelines to assess measures in your own city. Find the Assessment Tool and Guidelines at h2020-flow.eu/resources/publications.

The FLOW project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 635998.

PARTNERS

► For more information, see www.h2020-flow.eu or contact Project Coordinator Kristin Tovaas at k.tovaas@rupprecht-consult.eu or Bonnie Fenton at b.fenton@rupprecht-consult.eu [Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#) [YouTube](#)

AM4INFRA Final Conference

AM4INFRA FINAL CONFERENCE, A SIDE EVENT AT TRA2018!

After two years of extensive work, the AM4INFRA (Asset Management for Infrastructure) partners presented their (draft) results at the AM4INFRA final conference, held as a Side Event on 18th April 2018 at the Transport Research Arena 2018 (TRA2018) in Vienna.

PARTNERS

The AM4INFRA Final Conference was divided into two consecutive sessions with identical agendas in order to optimally facilitate the attendance. The first session was opened by Fabio Pasquali (ANAS) and the introduction of the AM4INFRA project concept and relevance was presented by Ramesh Sinhal (HE). The Project Coordinator Jenne van der Velde (RWS) and other project partners Ramesh Sinhal (HE), Elisabetta Marcovaldi (ANAS), Neng Mbah (HE) presented the outcomes of the three Living Labs: Rome, Eindhoven and London, in which the common framework approach was verified. During the second session, the welcome speech was given by Maria Cristina Marolda (EC DG MOVE) with the rest of the programme following the same format as the first session.

OUTCOMES OF THE LIVING LABS: ROME, EINDHOVEN AND LONDON

The “Living Lab” aims to provide the opportunity to embed and verify elements of the AM4INFRA framework approach into real life scenarios and practices. In the context of the AM4INFRA project, the Rome Living Lab, Eindhoven Living Lab and London Living Lab covered the three central themes of the project: cross asset optimisation, cross border optimisation and cross network optimisation through an examination of asset life cycle management and risk-based approaches. In total, around 100 participants joined these Living Labs, representing over 20 infrastructure agencies or affiliate organisations.

These three Living Labs produced a number of conclusions from both a technical and soft skills perspective. In summary, the application of these Living Labs succeeded in strengthening the cooperation and building convergence between infrastructure agencies and building a converging growing path, as well as providing inspiration, stimulating mutual learning and paving the way to a common language.

Living Lab	The main Scope
Living Lab Rome	<p>To demonstrate and validate the applicability and practicality of the asset data management approach;</p> <p>To provide recommendations for further improvement of asset data dictionary and Business Blueprint;</p> <p>To disseminate the AM4Infra initiative.</p>
Living Lab Eindhoven	<p>To demonstrate and verify the 'line of sight' framework in a cross border setting.</p>
Living Lab London	<p>To verify and demonstrate the six building block approach to risk and life cycle management within the common asset management framework.</p>

Motorway A90 in Rome.

LIVING LAB ROME - A90

The first AM4INFRA Living Lab was held on 31st January 2018 at the Sala Situazioni Nazionale, ANAS Headquarters in Rome, Italy. This Living Lab was concentrated on a 70 km stretch of the Rome Ringway A90.

The main scope:

- Demonstration and validation of the applicability and practicality of the asset data management approach;
- Recommendations for further improvement of asset data dictionary and Business Blueprint;
- Dissemination and outreach of the AM4Infra initiative.

Results:

1. Participants' agreement on AM4INFRA data and information framework.
2. Suggestions for new datasets for the Asset Data Dictionary and new links between them for system information model.
3. An asset-oriented and road user-oriented risk concept linked to maintenance works and level of service.
4. An opportunity to discuss the road corridor and criteria of the case study, based on a common asset management-life cycle costs approach.
5. A first identification of constraints/threats with respect to the common approach.

Motorway E34 along Eindhoven.

LIVING LAB - EINDHOVEN E34

The second, Eindhoven Living Lab, took place on 21st February in Antwerp, Belgium. The focal point of the Eindhoven Living Lab was cross-border optimisation. This motorway is a major artery connecting Antwerp and wider Flanders with the Netherlands and Germany further to the west.

The main scope:

To demonstrate and verify the 'line of sight' framework in a cross border setting.

Results:

1. **Opportunities were found in cross-border alignment** for planning of renovation works, future functionality, and lorry parking facilities
2. Mapping of **joint opportunities and issues**
3. **Get cross-border acquainted** is a hot topic
4. Helped to prepare **shortlist of priorities and required participants for follow-up Living Labs**

General conclusions:

- Cross-border issues are not isolated elements (in time, type of work, institutional players)
- Cross-border issues easily propagate deep into national networks (alternative routes/cross-modal solutions/parking facilities)
- Be aware of institutional asymmetry (mandate, responsibility, work culture etc)
- Language is important (meaning and terminology)

Motorway M4 in London

LIVING LAB - LONDON

The third, London Living Lab, took place in Old Windsor, close to London's Heathrow airport on 8-9th March 2018. This Living Lab was concentrated on the M4 (London - Wales) motorway - the main strategic route between London, the west of England and Wales.

The main scope:

To verify and demonstrate the six building block approach to risk and life cycle management within the common asset management framework.

Results:

1. **Helped understanding of the practical links** between the six building blocks (data, systems/tools, organisations and Whole Life Costs and managing risk)
2. **Management level/strategic systems are an important influence** on the effectiveness of asset management, not just operational and tactical levels
3. **A good opportunity** to discuss detailed topics and learn from each other

Life cycle management and risk-based approach framework - Six Building Blocks

For more information, see www.am4infra.eu or contact the Dissemination and Communication leader Adewole Adesiyun at adewole.adesiyun@fehrl.org [in](https://www.linkedin.com/in/adewoleadesiyun)

OVERVIEW OF RAGTIME MID-TERM RESULTS

The H2020 RAGTIME project has now reached its mid-term period, which gives an opportunity to look back on the past year and its achievements!

PARTNERS

DEVELOPMENT OF AN AAIM FRAMEWORK

Developing an advanced asset integrity management framework (AAIM), a review of European practices (legislations, best practices, tools, etc.) on asset management of transport infrastructure has been made. In addition, surveys and target interviews were conducted to identify specific management characteristics of transport infrastructures from the owner/operator perspective.

The most suitable Key performance indicators (KPI) were selected to assess and manage the different transport infrastructures to design the RAGTIME innovative management approach. The KPIs identified were classified according to five categories: four transport modes (road, rail, water and air), performance of transport infrastructure, whole life cycle of transport infrastructure, stakeholder's perspective, three RAGTIME modules: Financial, Economic and Risks, Technical Management and Governance.

FINANCIAL, ECONOMIC AND RISKS MODULE

The main objective is to define a comprehensive standardised multi-step methodology for evaluating and implementing risk assessment of transport infrastructure projects which the targeted stakeholder will be able to implement in its company through the guidance of a tool. To achieve this goal, the activity focuses on the definition of the risk assessment methodology through the three main steps of risk mapping, risk evaluation and risk strategy.

In particular, a specific three-step approach has been designed for the transport infrastructure specific sector which can combine the following elements: an integrated risk assessment approach during all phases of the life-cycle processes, a user-centred and user-friendly tool that could be used by any stakeholder involved in the project lifecycle, a dynamic monitoring system able to work in real-time whenever a risk is about to occur, appropriate strategies for risk mitigation with the main aim of minimising the impact that risks may have on the business.

TECHNICAL MANAGEMENT MODULE

The key features of technical Management Module: risk-based approach; infrastructural health monitoring (SHM); intervention & mitigation actions and linked to KPIs of the organisation. 104 technical risks or source of risks have been identified and classified into different categories: contractual, data, design & calculations, building & civil works, unintentional hazards, natural disasters and intentional threats. Level of service has been classified into five categories: green, cost-efficient, social/inclusive, resilient, safe/secure and risks to control the effectiveness of intervention and mitigation actions implemented.

GOVERNANCE MODULE

Governance Module focuses on new procurement process, which entails a new process for infrastructure acquisition, through: a new governance risk mitigation approach; the development of a new lean and innovative procurement process; the definition of a standard methodology for common evaluating the tenders from different administrations. Governance risks have been defined and represented through KPIs. A life cycle has been established based on the application of the Public Procurement of Innovative Products and Services, implementing lean and innovative procurement processes and creating a standard procurement methodology for the differ-

ent countries, all considering infrastructures as financial assets.

RAGTIME CLOUD-BASED PLATFORM FOR AAIM

RAGTIME Open Cloud platform architecture integrates existing AAIM tools and the new ones developed in the project, such as Governance tools, Risk and Finance Tools and Management Tools in order to support the envisaged RAGTIME platform functionality. Platform overcomes the current limitations for information flow and system interoperability, providing tools that cover all stages of the life cycle of the asset.

SECOND RAGTIME SRG MEETING

The second Stakeholders Reference Group (SRG) meeting was held on 26th February 2018 in Milan, Italy at RINA premises, organised by AON & RINA. Participants provided valuable feedback, comments about the use of decision aid methodology as well as (KPI) structures and instrumentation and infrastructure health monitoring integrated in a general workflow according to the RAGTIME approach. Given their strategic position and experience in transport infrastructure management, as well as contribution to the group was very relevant for RAGTIME project further development.

Second Stakeholders Reference Group meeting

For more information, see www.ragtime-asset.eu or contact Project Coordinator Maria Zalbide at maria.zalbide@tecnalia.com

Risk Management: Phases

SAFE-10-T STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP - DEFINING AN INTEGRATED USER DEMAND ANALYSIS AT NETWORK LEVEL

The H2020-funded SAFE-10-T project is developing a Decision Support Tool (DST) that can be employed to support decision-making regarding the management of transport infrastructure along the European TEN-T network. These decisions primarily relate to medium to long-term interventions on road, rail, and inland waterway transport infrastructure, to increase safety and maximise network capacity.

In order to ensure that all SAFE-10-T products respond efficiently to the actual needs of end-users (citizens, groups and organisations) and that they are equipped to accommodate future needs and scenarios, the SAFE-10-T project aims to:

- Identify the demands (current and future) of different transport users (freight, commute, leisure) of multi-modal transport networks;
- Identify current infrastructure capacity.

An integrated User Demand Analysis lies at the core of the SAFE-10-T project to identify the gaps between the existing infrastructure and future user demand for multi-modal transportation services. The research architecture for the elaboration of the analysis implies a comprehensive literature review on the state of the art in the SAFE-10-T partner countries, as well as several data collection activities (both quantitative and qualitative), that stretch from expert workshops to online surveys.

On Wednesday 16th May, the SAFE-10-T consortium organized the first Stakeholder Workshop in Zadar, Croatia, as a preliminary data collection activity for the development of the above-mentioned User Demand Analysis. The Workshop had a particular focus on selected demo project sites within the project:

1. The Port of Rotterdam, Netherlands

- North Sea – Baltic Corridor
- Freight transport

2. Rijeka harbour, Croatia

- Mediterranean Corridor
- Tourism route

3. The Severn crossing, UK

- Urban interchange

The workshop pursued a twofold objective:

- To implement a participatory review of the main dimensions and variables upon which the data collection activities will be focused (i.e. dimensions and variables identified by means of the literature review, in the first phase of the project).
- To gather insights in relation to the existing tools to understand user demand currently implemented in the industry, for the 3 case studies at stake.

During the workshop sessions, participants debated upon the relevance of identified dimensions and variables for the specific case studies, as well as upon the available sources for data collection at national and regional level.

The gathered insights play a crucial role in the finalisation of the data collection tools and of the data collection process, to be launched in the forthcoming project phase.

Beyond its essential role in shaping the future research steps, the workshop represented an added value for the overall SAFE-10-T consortium, in terms of the direct involvement of stakeholders and end-users in the development of the projects' products.

SAFE-10-T project team

SAFE-10-T Stakeholder Workshop

In addition, The SAFE-10-T project organised a Special Session on the first day of the 5th International Conference on Road and Rail Infrastructure (CETRA 2018) which was held on 17th May 2018. The session presented the four following topics:

1. Monitoring and Modelling of Critical Infrastructure by Lorcan Connolly
2. Multi-modal network analysis by Irina Stipanovic
3. Global safety framework by Kenneth Gavin
4. Demonstration projects by Paul Doherty and Julie Clarke

PARTNERS

► For more information see www.safe10tproject.eu or contact Project Coordinator Paul Doherty at pdoherty@gdgeo.com

AEROBI DEMONSTRATES THE SECOND VERSION OF AERIAL ROBOTIC SYSTEM IN SEVILLE!

The H2020 AEROBI project aims to develop an incrementally optimised aerial robotic system with a multi-joint arm for the in-depth inspection and assessment of reinforced concrete bridges that will include the computer vision system, sensor system and laser equipment, while it will be integrated with the software to evaluate and structurally assess the mechanical performance and safety of the inspected bridges.

After two years of work, the Aerial Robotic System was second time field evaluated and demonstrated on 19th March on a bridge near Seville, Spain. The main focus of this trial was to demonstrate three different platforms which cover the most important end-user requirements.

During the second trial the operational capabilities were studied, especially in terms of navigation and user-friendliness to prepare the final version that will be tested on Egnatia motorway bridges, in East Macedonia, Greece for the final demonstration.

Three platforms were tested:

1. VISUAL INSPECTION ON COMPLETE BRIDGE

- Crack detection
- Other types of damage detection (like spalling and corrosion)
- GPS-free localization; short term autonomous navigation

2. CONTACT INSPECTIONS USING AN AUTONOMOUS ROBOTIC DEVICE

- Crack depth measurement (standalone tool test)
 - Precise positioning of contact tool using a total station: Pier inclination, span deflection, etc.
- Autonomous flight during the contact operation. Displacement of the contact tool controlled by the inspection operator. Assisted flying mode if not in contact.

3. PRECISE POSITION OF DIFFERENT STRUCTURES OF THE BRIDGE

- Span deflection
- Autonomous operation using a total station

Major achievements in the project so far:

- Aerial robot and its integrated robotic arm adapted for bridge inspection and preliminary tests.
- Developed two alternative lightweight prototypes: a stick-to-ceiling UAV and a UAV with a compliant arm, which have been tested in flight.
- Second demonstration of Hypotheses generation for defects (March 2018)
- Version 2 of computer vision system for defect classification (March 2018)
- Laboratory testing of the crack depth measurement prototype. Prototype ready for integration on the robotic arm of the aerial vehicle.
- Fabrication and testing of the crack width measurement module prototype based on optomechanical pressure measurements on fiber-optic fan-out connector.
- Development of a fabrication process suitable for manufacturing carbonized resist layers to be used for opto-acoustic emission in the rebar and voids ultrasonic measurement module.
- Preliminary tests on profile measurements by prisms optically connected to a total station and manipulated by an aerial vehicle.

Second AEROBI trial in Seville

PARTNERS

For more information, please contact Project Coordinator Philippe Chrobocinski at philippe.chrobocinski@airbus.com or see www.aerobi.eu

2ND SENSKIN WORKSHOP HELD ON 24-25TH MAY 2018 IN ISTANBUL, TURKEY

Following the first workshop held in Brussels, Belgium on 8th November 2017 (as reported in the last issue of this magazine), the H2020 SENSKIN project held its second workshop entitled “SENSKIN Bridge Monitoring System - Prototype Field Tests” at Le Meridien İstanbul Etiler hotel in Istanbul, Turkey, on 24-25th May. About 75 participants from three continents attended from the field of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), including local stakeholders and academics. This event, organised by Turkish project member KGM, was held a week after the pre-installation of the first pilot on the first Bosphorus bridge in Istanbul.

A number of very interesting discussions took place during the four sessions on 24th May 2018. The second day of the workshop on 25th May featured a visit to the installation site.

SESSION 1: BRIDGE MONITORING - CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Moderated by Claudia Ciuca, FEHRL Project Officer, this session included an introduction by Project Manager Kostas Bouklas of ICCS, an overview of the Latest Developments and Challenges in SHM systems by Serdar Soyöz of Boğaziçi University Istanbul, Turkey and the Egnatia Motorway Sensing Systems by Panagiotis Panetsos of Egnatia Odos AE, Greece.

SESSION 2: BRIDGE MONITORING SYSTEMS - USERS' NEEDS AND CHALLENGES

This session, moderated by Kostas Bouklas, started with a presentation of “Monitoring System of Suspension Bridges in Turkey” by Sabri Tekin, Head of Motorways Department, KGM, Turkey, and followed with “SHM System in 3rd Bosphorus Bridge (Yavuz Sultan Selim Bridge)” by Mehmet İzgi, Bridge Contractor, ICA, BOT Project, Turkey, “Bridge Monitoring Systems and Challenges in

Ukraine” by Ihor Babyak of DNDI, Ukraine and “Bridge Monitoring in UK” by Peter Jones of TRL, UK.

SESSION 3: SENSKIN SYSTEM - FIELD APPLICATIONS

The third session gave an overview of field applications of the SENSKIN system and was moderated by Fatma Orhan of KGM. The following presentations were given:

- Overall SENSKIN System and Technical Capabilities by Kostas Bouklas
- Laboratory tests on SENSKIN Prototype by Peter Jones
- Preliminary activities and preparation for the SENSKIN installation in Bosphorus Bridge by Rahşan Yıldırım Telek of KGM, Turkey
- SENSKIN Field application at Bosphorus 1 bridge, Turkey - Installation and Data Interpretation by Eleni Cheilakou and Nassos Anastasopoulos of MGH, Greece
- System installation and validation in Egnatia Motorway, Greece by Panagiotis Panetsos
- Acoustic Emission for Structural Health Monitoring by Nassos Anastasopoulos and Jon Watson of MGH

SESSION 4: PANEL DISCUSSION

The final session, moderated by Sabri Tekin of KGM, featured an introduction entitled “SHM System Evolution of Monitoring System” by Dyab Khazem/Oğuz Ertekin of the Parsons Transportation Group Inc, USA, Turkey Office. A panel discussion then took place with panellists Kostas Bouklas, Peter Jones, Rahşan Yıldırım Telek and Nassos Anastasopoulos.

All materials, including a new A4 brochure produced specifically for the workshop and onwards, can be found at www.senskin.eu/events/second-senskinworkshop.

PRE-INSTALLATION OF PILOT

On 17th-18th May, KGM facilitated the access and permission for project partners MGH and ICCS to carry out the pre-installation of five conventional and five SENSKIN sensors on the first Bosphorus bridge for the first pilot. On the second day of the workshop, participants visited this installation and listened to a short presentation on how the system stores and checks the data on the spot. ICCS then replied to questions and made the final adjustments to the sensor, as it was set to be uninstalled from the bridge. A discussion on the maintenance of the bridge was also held.

The second pilot will be held in September 2018 on the Egnatia Motorway ravine bridge G4 in Krysalopigi, Greece. For more information, contact Project Coordinator

Angelos Amditis at a.amditis@iccs.gr or see www.senskin.eu

PARTNERS

FIRST HALF OF SKILLFUL PROJECT: TRAINING & EDUCATION SCHEMES AND FUTURE PILOTING TESTING

One of the main goals of the 36-month SKILLFUL (Skills and competences development of future transportation professionals at all levels) H2020 project is to structure the key specifications and components of curricula and training schemes and courses, aiming at the education and training of transport professionals, in order to be able to meet the new and future needs of this sector, in several levels and fields, stemming from the existing, emerging and future changes and developments that take place in the European transportation sector.

PARTNERS

The developments of various aspects of the transportation sector, such as game changers, technological changes, appearance of new services and new business schemes, as well as societal factors, have also been studied and analysed within the first half of the SKILLFUL project, which has just been completed. The outcomes coming from this analysis, along with the analysis made on the status of the training programmes of transportation professionals in Europe, have been put together to create a description of the existing, emerging and future knowledge and skills requirements of workers at all levels of the transportation sector.

For this purpose, the following five different knowledge creation activities have been organised related to the development of the training courses:

1. Transport infrastructure operators' training schemes.
2. Young scientists' seminars.
3. Lifelong training schemes for low to middle-skilled segments of transport professionals.
4. Interdisciplinary thematic courses on key technologies, services and trends.
5. Towards a pan-European Transport master curriculum.

The 34 training schemes courses and curricula that have been designed and developed within the SKILLFUL project, come to address the needs described above, covering in good balance all the above knowledge creation activities.

From these courses, 17 will be piloted within the project during the coming months, again covering all knowledge creation activity types, in order for these training schemes to be assessed by experts and users and prove the project's concept and methodologies, as well as to evaluate its future impacts.

In a nutshell, SKILLFUL pilots will be implemented in 13 pilot sites in 11 different countries (namely Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain and UK). The pilots will cover all modes, while also a wide variety of transport occupations, focusing mainly to the middle skilled workers. The courses will be piloted either at university or vocational level, depending on the target audience and the course's objectives and expected outcomes.

Moreover, during the next period of SKILLFUL and in parallel to the implementation of the pilots, new roles of business actors that will facilitate the training process and enhance sustainability, will be proposed and their profiles are going to be fully developed.

For more information, see www.skillfulproject.eu or contact Project Coordinator Thierry Goger at thierry.goger@fehrl.org

TRA VISIONS 2018 AWARDED PRIZES TO YOUNG AND SENIOR RESEARCHERS AT TRA 2018

The EC-funded TRA VISIONS 2018 competition awarded prizes to both its young and senior researcher winners at two separate ceremonies at the 2018 Transport Research Arena (TRA 2018), held from 16-19th April 2018 in Vienna, Austria.

YOUNG RESEARCHER WINNERS

Overall, 169 young researchers from 56 different European universities participated in the Young Researchers Competition and submitted 122 ideas for the transport modes road, rail, waterborne and cross-modal. The prizes were awarded for this competition during the TRA2018 Opening Ceremony on Monday 16th April (12-12:30pm). Prizes were sponsored by industry (ALICE, ERTRAC, Meyer Werft, SHIFT2RAIL and UITP).

IN THE ROAD SECTOR, THE WINNERS WERE

- Mareike Hedderich from Munich University of the Federal Armed Forces (Park Spot Routing)
- Irene Martinez from Universidad Politecnica de Catalunya (Location of Variable Speed Limit application area to avoid capacity drop)
- Federico Perrotta from University of Nottingham (Evaluation of road pavements fuel efficiency using truck sensors data).

IN THE RAIL SECTOR, THE WINNERS WERE

- Sander Van Aken (team leader)
- Patrick Looij and Nikola Besinovic from Delft University of Technology (Optimising Railway Timetables for Maintenance Possessions)
- Bernhard Reinholz from Hochschule München (Using braking energy in diesel locomotives)
- Robin Severs from Coventry University (Customer Experience and Exclusion of Smaller Towns in Intercity High Speed Rail Networks)

IN THE WATERBORNE SECTOR, THE WINNERS WERE

- Carlo Augusto Pasquucci from Università di Genova (Free Form Deformation and Surrogate Surface: a Help in Greener Ship Design)
- Emmanouil-loizos Tsougranis from Newcastle University (Pressurised SOFC-GT Electric Propulsion Power Plant for LNG vessels)
- Syed Marzan Ul Hasan from University of Liege (A Method for Optimizing Cruising Speed Profile using Coasting Phenomena for an Eco-Friendly Ship)

FINALLY, IN THE CROSS-MODALITY SECTOR, THE WINNERS WERE

- Tomas Ambra from Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Potential of supply chain collaboration in Brussels: up-scaling performance of demonstration case)

- Katrin Lättman from Karlstad University (Capturing the human dimension of accessibility in transport)
- Julian Bock from RWTH Aachen University (Intersection Dataset from UAV Video Data for Automated Driving).

SENIOR RESEARCHER WINNERS

The Senior Researcher winners received their awards during the TRA2018 Gala Dinner on Tuesday 16th April. The competition received 121 entries from researchers based at 91 institutions, universities or companies. Entries were submitted for the four transport modes road, rail, waterborne and cross-modality.

- In the road sector, the winner was Ludwig Buergler from AVL LIST GmbH based in Graz for his work on diesel engine combustion.
- The rail winner was Ken Gavin from Ireland currently working at the Delft University of Technology and has a sustained track record of railway infrastructure research.
- Osman Turan from Strathclyde University in Scotland was the winner in the waterborne sector and he is recognised for his research on ship safety and human factors.
- The fourth winner was Verena Ehrler from the DLR Institute of Transport Research in Berlin and she is acknowledged for her continued and outstanding contribution to EU funded transport research related to cross modality.

PARTNERS

► For more information, contact **George Smyrnakis** at george.smyrnakis@newcastle.ac.uk, look up **TRA Visions** on Facebook, Twitter or Linked In or see www.travisions.eu

4TH OCTOBER 2018

Infravation

An Infrastructure Innovation Programme

COME AND JOIN US

AT THE ERA-NET PLUS INFRAVATION

FINAL CONFERENCE

8.30am – 12pm, 4th October 2018 -
Rotterdam Marriott Hotel, Weena 686, 3012 CN Rotterdam

Register today from www.infravation.net/events/Final_conference for the Infravation Final Conference on the morning of Thursday 4th October 2018 at the Rotterdam Marriott Hotel, Weena 686, 3012 CN Rotterdam.

This event will cover presentations by the Management Group and each of the nine Project Coordinators. This event will be followed by other related events:

Thursday 4th October, afternoon (as of 1.15pm): one-hour Infravation slot at Innovation Expo 2018, 'RDM Onderzeebootloods' (former submarine construction hall) in Rotterdam

Thursday 4th October (7pm): Infravation closing joint dinner (Steering Group members, Scientific Panel members and Infravation Project Coordinators)

Friday 5th October 2018: Rijkswaterstaat, Boompjes 200, 3011 XD Rotterdam

- 08:30-10:25 Infravation Steering Group
- 10:35-12:00 Joint meeting Scientific Panel and Project Coordinators

► See www.infravation.net or contact the Call Manager, Richard van der Elburg at richard.vander.elburg@rws.nl for more information [Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#)

26-28TH MARCH 2019

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FIRM 19
FEHRL Infrastructure Research Meeting
26-28 March 2019

Join us at the FEHRL Infrastructure Research Meeting 2019 (FIRM19) on 26-28th March 2019 at the BluePoint Centre, 80 Bd A. Reyers, 1030 Brussels. Register today and get more information at www.fehrl.org/knowledge-transfer/events/firm2019 and contact Angélica Coldibeli at angelica.coldibeli@fehrl.org with any questions.

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